

Policy Cloud

Cloud for Data-Driven Policy Management

CLOUD FOR DATA-DRIVEN POLICY MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: This deliverable will include the specification of the tools used to model and design the policies as well as the design of the policy development toolkit, and the mechanisms required for the compilation of policies collections to perform cross-sector analysis and policy making. It will also architect the tools to identify groups for data-driven policies experimentation and adaptation.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
BDA	Big Data Analytics
DAA	Data Acquisition and Analytics
DPA	Data Processing Agreement
DSS	Decision Support System
EC	European Commission
GDPR	Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons regarding the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation)
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PDT	Policy Development Toolkit
PM	Policy Model
PME	Policy Model Editor
PP	Public Policy
SOA	Service Oriented Architecture
UC	Use Case
UI	User Interface
UX	User eXperience
UML	Unified Modelling Language

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Executive Summary

This document is an incremental update of deliverables “D5.2 Cross-sector Policy Lifecycle Management: Design and Open Specification 1”, September 2020, and “D5.4 Cross-sector Policy Lifecycle Management: Design and Open Specification 2”, August 2021. It details the specification of the tools and technologies used to model Public Policies (PPs) as well as the design of the policy development toolkit (including the visualization framework), and the mechanisms required for compilation of policy collections to perform cross-sector analysis. The purpose of this series of deliverables is to keep track of the specifications throughout the project and update them as the project progresses.

This deliverable is the last of the series, has been released in M32 (August 2022) of the project, and its main objective is to describe the approach to the policy modelling and validation that will support policy makers in the design, evaluation, optimization and adaptation of policies. The Policy Development Toolkit (PDT), along with the Policy Model Editor (PME), constitute the front-end of the PolicyCLOUD platform, which allows policy makers to create, update and validate policies. The PDT backend, which hides the complexity of storing the data models into persistent storage, implements the services that the front-end uses to display the content to the user and provide the necessary user experience.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope

This document is the third and final iteration of “Cross-Sector Policy Lifecycle Management: Design and Open Specifications”, and covers the work done in this regard in tasks T5.2, T5.3, T5.4 and T5.5. Its main purpose is to provide the updated approach to the policy modelling and evaluation that will be used in PolicyCLOUD to support policy makers in the creation, modelling, and evaluation of their Public Policies.

In this document, we will continue to refer to Use Case #4, even if the London Borough of Camden left the project and the Use Case lead by this partner is no longer active. We will mention it in order to explain the work done and how it helped in the design of the structure of the platform.

1.2 Summary of changes

The main changes in the current and final version of the deliverable are the enhancements/revisions/updates made in every Section of the document. For the final iteration of this deliverable, we decided to keep the overall structure as it was in Deliverable D5.4.

1.3 Structure of the Document

The rest of the document is structured as follows:

- **Section 2** introduces the definition of Public Policies (PPs), including state-of-the-art concepts on PPs development that cover why, what, and how they are developed and who is actively or passively affected by the policies.
- **Section 3** presents the conceptual methodologies proposed for policy modelling, based mainly on the concepts of ontology and semantic reasoning technologies. It also proposes an updated approach on policy modelling and their evaluation based on the concept of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).
- **Section 4** describes the mechanisms required for compilation of policy collections / clusters to perform cross-sector analysis.
- **Section 5** introduces the architecture of the Policy Development Toolkit (PDT) and describes the various User Interfaces (UIs) components, including the Data Visualization Framework.
- **Section 6** details the legal and ethical considerations and requirements.
- **Section 7** provides the conclusion of the document.

2 Public Policies

A *public policy* (PP) is a plan, course of action, or set of regulations adopted by a policy maker to influence and determine decisions or procedures that affect a group of public and private actors in order to achieve a desired outcome. The policy maker gathers information through public consultation and scientific research to extract the necessary knowledge base and creates a policy, or a set of policies, which serve to define and promote a preferred course of action (or inaction). This, in turn, will allow targets and points of reference to be established for the short and medium term. In PolicyCLOUD, we include, within the concept of “policy makers”, government bureaucrats and technocrats from various sectors (e.g., healthcare, education, security, environment, etc.) and public sector staff who implement and evaluate programs.

A PP is carried out following a defined process, considering the context and characteristics of the geographic area (city, region, country) where it must be implemented, with the purpose of driving the PP’s content. PPs will pertain to some actors, which must be considered during their design. When a PP is developed, a proper evaluation process shall be defined to assess whether the actions or inactions considered are fulfilling the defined goals. The evaluation process includes the definition and measurement of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to assess if the proposed goals are reached (and to what extent), and to evaluate if the correct parameters were selected to meet this goal. KPIs are generally presented to a group of key actors that are interested in the results of the PPs, in order to decide whether to continue with the same policies, apply corrective measures, or to partially or completely redefine the content of the PPs. This schema is illustrated in Figure 1, as proposed by Gagnon and Labonté [3].

FIGURE 1 – POLICY ANALYSIS FRAMEWORK

2.1 Actors

Actors are defined as individuals, groups, or organizations that are relevant decision-makers and/or parties interested in monitoring the effect and evolution of a PP that has been created or modified.

In PolicyCLOUD, we group actors in two categories, depending on their ability to take decisions when formulating the content of a PP:

- **formal actors** are defined as actors who belong to the public authorities at any level (local, regional, national, international) and are responsible for the definition of the PPs and, thus, have formal political power or are direct policy makers;
- **informal actors** are defined as actors who do not have any political power and, thus, are outside of the decision-making process, but can still have a scientific or political influence on the final decisions, such as the civil society, NGOs, etc.

The PolicyCLOUD project will be mainly focused on formal actors, since the goal of the project is to serve as a Decision Support System (DSS) for policy making. This does not mean, however, that policy making using the PolicyCLOUD system will be performed without considering the input from other relevant stakeholders. Indeed, informal actors could be considered as key entities or groups for the purpose of evaluating the KPIs. Hence, PolicyCLOUD will consider which actors should be informed on the results of the KPIs related to the PP developed.

2.2 Context

The context of a PP defines why the PP is needed and refers to those cultural, structural, situational and/or external factors relevant to the PP and which may have a relevant effect on a given society.

- **Cultural factors** refer to the existence of formal/informal hierarchies, different languages or ethnic minorities that may affect the equity of a PP, gender role, and the importance of religious factors, among others.
- **Structural factors** are stable elements of the society, such as the political system, the level of participation of the civil society in the discussion and decision process, the economic system, etc.
- **Situational factors** are temporary conditions, such as epidemics, natural disasters, or austerity measures in times of economic crisis, that may also have an influence on PPs and/or affect the monitoring of PPs in temporary situations.
- **Other factors** refer to conditions of inter-dependence between states, cooperation among organizations/states or international laws and norms that may affect PPs.

The full context of PPs is not directly integrated in the policy modelling tasks of PolicyCLOUD, since this cannot be modelled directly. However, the PolicyCLOUD system will encourage policy makers to consider all the relevant contextual factors before developing any PP.

2.3 Content

The content refers to the main subject-matter of the PP, and to which questions are considered in the design of the PP. The content of a PP defines specific issues, problems and/or challenges and is linked directly to the domain it applies (e.g., security – Use Case#1, agri-food – Use Case #2, mobility and transport – Use Case #3, and employment – Use Case #4). Some examples for each domain are provided below:

Security:

- How to improve accessibility of data on radicalized individuals and groups
- How to increase efficient use of resources (e.g., number of restrictive measures to optimize a cost efficient stop of radicalization spreading)

- How to promote a better inclusion of different groups in the society (e.g., dedicated programmes and activities targeting specific groups, such as immigrants or minorities)

Agri-food:

- What trends exist in the wine sector
- How to increase sales in an increasingly competitive market
- How to increment the market of the D.O. Aragon product show
- How to increase efficient use of resources for marketing activities

Mobility and transport:

- How to efficiently allocate resources
- How to proactively target areas for preventive measures
- How to improve transport and parking utilisation and customer experience
- How to identify trends and problem concentration areas

Employment

- How different groups of the population are affected by unemployment
- How to predict future trends and potential problems

The content of a PP cannot be separated from the dimension of the process (how the PP is carried out), the actors (who define the PP and need to be informed on its evolution), the context (where the PP will be implemented and what specificities it should have), the stakeholders (who are affected by the PP), and the evaluation (what impact is the PP having, as measured by KPIs that should have been defined previously).

The purpose of the PolicyCLOUD project is to support policy makers in developing the content of the PP as an evidence-based outcome of the PolicyCLOUD system.

2.4 Process

The process defines how the PP was brought forward and implemented. The process of policy making can be seen as a methodology or approach that is defined by seven phases, which extends the policy analysis cycles provided by Patton and Sawicki 1993 [4] (see Figure 2):

FIGURE 2 – POLICY ANALYSIS PROCESS

In the first phase, the policy maker **defines and details the given problem** by characterizing the social context in which the problem is embedded and identifying the independent variables that affect policy outcomes. It is the role of the policy maker to understand the positions and influence of various stakeholders and to choose the definition that the problem owner/decision maker has control on. Clarification of the problem takes place with consultation, brainstorming, narratives, and scientific research.

In the second phase, the policy maker **identifies the evaluation criteria** that determine when the problem is solved or a goal is accomplished. She/he will select those criteria that are central to the problem and most relevant to the decision makers in the implementation process [4].

Once the policy maker knows the values, objectives, and goals of the stakeholders and the evaluation criteria for validating the policies, she/he can generate a list of possible policies. This list is usually long since there are many variations and combinations. Benchmarking and past experience are common approaches for **identifying policy alternatives** to be implemented [5] [4].

Among policy alternatives, the most appropriate options are selected using the already defined evaluation criteria, leading thus to the **formulation of the policy**. The different alternatives are assessed based on the potential impact and their chain of causation. Since not every policy can be tested with the same method, various methods (e.g., cost–benefit analysis, programming, institutional analysis, and quantitative analysis) to evaluate different policies can be used.

The next phase is **policy implementation**. This is the most important phase, since it is aimed at setting up the public authority’s planned actions in the way intended by the PP, to achieve the expected impact and results. In most instances, the policy maker develops implementation guidelines and procedures rather than being directly involved in the implementation of the selected PP.

The final phase is the **monitoring and evaluation** of the implemented PP. This requires the involvement of both formal and informal actors. In particular, this phase is about monitoring the use of inputs and the achievement of outputs, as well as evaluating the direct effects and medium-/long-term impacts of the PP, to provide evidence on whether the PP is achieving its objectives. It is important for the policy maker to know whether a failed PP did not achieve the intended results because it was not implemented as designed, or because the PP’s underlying theory was incorrect [4].

Although in common daily practice these stages lack clear separation, the PolicyCLOUD system is mainly devoted to directly helping the policy maker in the policy creation and decision-making stages, as well as, indirectly, in the policy implementation and policy evaluation stages.

2.5 Impact

Proper information management and monitoring is of utmost importance to enhance decision-making and to monitor and track the evolution of a PP that has been implemented. A useful tool in this regard is the definition and measurement of the KPIs, as described in the above paragraphs. KPIs are metrics that are determined through scientific evidence or through the consensus of experts (when evidence is unavailable) to provide feedback to key actors about the results being achieved and to use this information to improve PPs.

Information is a key resource for developing specific KPIs that enable the measurement of each goal. KPIs are also a tool that needs to be reported for accountability reasons to those agents who may be responsible or who must take informed decisions on existing PPs and their possible updates. In addition, to develop good indicators, a set of common criteria could be used to aid the experts and final users in reaching a consensus on which indicators should be considered. To this end, the KPIs should be valid, specific, measurable, reliable, evidence-based, achievable, feasible, relevant, time-bounded, i.e., reported at regular intervals.

The benefits of using KPIs are several, including mainly the ability to assess the outcomes of PPs, the ability to compare equal parameters among different organizations following a benchmarking process of sharing improvements, the promotion of accountability to relevant actors, the promotion of transparency (e.g., by allowing a public reporting of results), and the identification of areas for further research.

An example of a KPI from an existing PP from Use Case #2 is provided below.

Business KPIs	Success indicators
Increased brand awareness and reputation in social media	Number of posts, comments, retweets
Identified the most interesting concepts and trends in wine markets	Number of new terms identified Number of influencers identified
Brand analysis: quality vs price vs taste	
Prediction analysis: quality of the next crop	

TABLE 1 – DEFINITION OF THE KPIS FOR THE USE CASE OF ARAGON (AGRIFOOD)

3 Policy Modelling and Configuration

3.1 Modelling Methodologies

3.1.1 Ontologies

Policy modelling and decision-making knowledge is often represented as a set of basic definitions such as alternatives, criteria, decision matrices, and decisions themselves. However, this domain is much richer, and many other related notions are useful for making the right decisions: preferences, weights, thresholds, and so on. This knowledge must be formalized within a model. In addition, the practical needs for policy making as well as the research dealing with decision-making, are increasingly growing as, for instance, in Information System engineering.

This kind of modelling is justified by the necessity to show different semantic links existing between policy making concepts. We have elaborated the ontology to represent concepts of the policy making domain, as well as their properties and relations.

The starting point for analysing the ontology (see Figure 3) is the situation. The situation is an abstract concept that puts together the main elements and describes a set of specific conditions dealing with a given object. The object is an artifact which is the subject of decision-making.

Activity	Expense	Sub partial Item
Budget	Expenses Classifier	Subprogram
Budget Analytic	Expense Object	Program Executer Unit (UEP)
Budget Approved	Finality Function	Programmatic Category
Budget Project Draft	Financial Administration	Project
Budget Synthetic	Financing Source	Public Funds Administrative Service (SAFOP)
Budget States	Geographic Locate	Rector Organism
Budgetary Classifier	Institutional	Resource
Budgetary Fiscal Year	Institutional	Resources Estimation
Budgetary Policy	Jurisdiction	Year Financial Administrative Service (SAF)
Budgetary Top	Program	
Executer Organism	Program	

TABLE 2 – KEY TERMS

3.1.2 Semantic reasoning and querying

Semantic queries allow for queries and analytics of an associative and contextual nature. Semantic queries enable the retrieval of both explicitly and implicitly derived information based on syntactic, semantic, and structural information contained in a policy data store. They are designed to deliver precise results (possibly the distinctive selection of one single piece of information) or to answer fuzzier and wide-open questions through pattern matching and digital reasoning.

Semantic queries work on named graphs, linked data, or triples. This enables the query to process the actual relationships between information and infer answers from the network of data. From a technical point of view, semantic queries are precise relational-type operations much like a database query. They work on structured data and therefore have the possibility to utilize comprehensive features like operators (e.g., >, < and =), namespaces, pattern matching, sub-classing, transitive relations, semantic rules, and contextual full text search.

The system will be able to automatically integrate data from different sources by replacing the context-dependent keys in the JSON output with URLs pointing to semantic vocabularies that will be used to represent and link the data.

3.2 Policy Modelling

3.2.1 Data model

A *policy model (PM)* is an instantiation of the data model. At the second development phase of the project, the data model that we relied on in the first phase has been updated to include the entity of a *domain* that is related with various already defined entities, and to update the definition of the *data model* and *Analytical Tool* that is being currently used, after integration of the *Policy Model Editor (PME)* with the *Data Analytics and Acquisition (DAA)* layer implemented under the scope of WP4 activities. The current definition of the PM can be depicted in the following class diagram.

FIGURE 4 – POLICY MODEL CLASS DIAGRAM

From the class diagram, it can be concluded that there are several *entities* that are involved in a PM, and each one of those can be reused by other models. The central entity is the *policy* which holds all information regarding the specific model. This might be assigned to a specific policy maker, thus making this instance private to her/him, or might be public, thus being a model for the creation of new policies. This also allows the policy maker to search and explore her/his own policies. Each policy is associated with a list of available *KPIs*, which defines the qualitative and quantitative indicators of the policy. KPIs are related to specific goals per stakeholder. It is important to highlight that our design

enables the re-usability of KPIs, such that a well-defined KPI can be also used by other policies. As a result, there is a many-to-many relationship between the *policies* and the *KPIs* that allows for this to happen.

Moreover, each KPI is validated by a list of analytical tools that performs the processing and produces the results. The analytical tools might be of different types (e.g., sentiment analysis, opinion mining, risk assessment, etc.) and can be related with one or many different data sources. Therefore, an analytical tool is not implemented and locked-in for a specific data source, but can be a general-purpose tool applied to several data models.

The data model has been further extended in this third phase of the project by including the *domain* entity. The latter is related with various other entities, such as the *policy*, *kpi*, *actor* and *stakeholder*. This allows the PME to retrieve existing *policies*, *kpis* etc. according to the domain they are associated with. To have a formal way for all these entities to be filtered and returned to the PME, we put this information in a separate entity that holds a list of supported domains.

A main differentiator between the current design and the one we relied on in the first phase of the project, is that the information related with the entity *analytical tool* is not stored in the persistent storage that the PME uses. Instead, this information is dynamically retrieved by the DAA layer. The analytic provider registers her/his tool to the DAA by using the mechanisms developed under WP4, and the DAA layer publishes programmatically this type of information. The latter includes the endpoint to be invoked in order to trigger the execution of the analytical processing, the input parameters that require etc. This information is collected by the PDT via the invocation of a REST interface and is represented by the *AnalyticalToolConfiguration* entity of the data model. Moreover, as each of the tools might be configured differently according to its purpose (i.e., it might be able to return results in different formats to be visualized by different graphs), the *AnalyticalTool* entity contains the specific information on how the tool will be instantiated to be used by the *KPI* that is related to.

Finally, when an analytical tool is invoked, this submits a *job* for execution. Since the processing of a dataset can be a long-running process, the invocation of tools is asynchronous. Therefore, a new *job* is created, and when the analysis is concluded, the result of the job is stored in persistent storage.

To summarize, this data model for policies allows for great flexibility, as it avoids duplicating entities and instead, it allows for the re-usability and the addition of new elements that can be offered in the ecosystem. A policy maker can have a list of *policies*, or explore the *PMs*, validate the existing KPIs that might be applied in different domains, and investigate why some of them can be beneficial across domain sectors, and why others are more related to specific ones. The proposed solution also allows for the provision of additional analytical tools that can be developed in the future and can be easily plugged into the platform and made available to any existing PM. Their retrieval is being done dynamically by requesting them from the underlying DAA layer. That way, the provider of the data analytics has to register the tool once, and this can be then discovered by the upper layers, which model this information accordingly. This gives an absolute freedom for the policy maker to validate different aspects and KPIs using a variety of different tools.

3.2.2 Policy Model Editor

The Policy Model Editor (PME) is a component that lies on the PDT. It is a client application for the PDT backend service to store policies into the policy repository.

FIGURE 5: PME ARCHITECTURE

The main goal of the PME is to simplify the creation and the modification of a Policy so with the other components of PDT to be able to give the ability to the end user to create and evaluate a Policy in a iterative cycle of modification and evaluation as long as it is needed.

The main steps of this process are the:

- Policy description and categorization by Domain.
- Relate existing KPIs with the Policy (re-usability)
- New KPIs composition for the Policy
- Review and save the Policy
- Run the Policy with the PDT Policy Wizard
- Result visualization with the PDT Data Visualization Framework

FIGURE 6: POLICY MODEL LIFECYCLE

The most important step in PME is the creation of new KPIs. This is a procedure where the user has to define the goal, the actors and the stakeholders for the KPI, select the appropriate Data Source and Analytical Tool, and finally fill those parameters that the Analytical Tool requires to run.

In this step PME helps the user to create a valid KPI and provides a user-friendly environment that hides the complexity of this entity. For instance like the parameters, which are explained later in the Policy Wizard section ([Figure 17](#) – Class diagram of the parameters), achieved by the adaptivity of the user interface which follows the user selection of Analytical Tool, by providing help with pop-up dialogs and hints, and by pointing out the necessary fields that have not been filled in by the user throughout the Policy Model editing process, as shown in the figures below.

Parameters

param_name ^

param_description	Value Type	Input Type	
Unit			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Required
MONTHS	STRING	VARIABLE	

Constraints

Constraint Type	Value
DEFAULT	default value

Parameter Value

Evaluation Type	Value
<div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 2px; display: inline-block; background-color: #f0f0f0;"> EQUAL </div>	NOVEMBER
GREATER	
GREATER_OR_EQUAL	
LESS	
LESS_OR_EQUAL	

FIGURE 7: PARAMETER USER CONTROL

PDT - Policy Model Editor

Specify the Data Model for the KPI Element

In this section you specify the data model for the KPI Element.

Starting by naming the data model

Name *

Name the model

this field cannot be longer than 255 characters length.

Then select the source of the data that will be analyzed from the analytical tool

Data Source *

tweet-carinena

Select Data Source

Optionally you can provide some information for the data model, this field cannot be longer than 255 characters length.

Info

Provide information about the Data Model (optional)

Next you must select the Analytical Tool

Select Analytical Tool *

SentimentAggregator

and the visualization Graph that projects to the user

Graph *

TIME_SERIES

Select the graph output

After the Analytical Tool selection the parameters for this tool will be displayed and must be filled if that demanded by the parameter

Parameters

start_date

Close

[back to Search and select existing Key Performance Indicators](#)
[Preview and submit the P](#)

FIGURE 8: POPUP HELP DIALOGUE

FIGURE 9: VALIDATION HINTS

4 Policy Collections and Cross-Sector Analysis

The main goal of the policy collections sub-component is to enable the development of collection / clusters of policies that will be used to retrieve relevant information for cross-sector analysis and therefore to compute the associated KPIs within the policy evaluation component.

Identification of the proper collection / cluster of policies is based on a set of inclusion and exclusion criteria, which are used to calculate the KPI used to evaluate the policies through the execution of the analytical models, regardless of their nature, i.e., single, aggregated, composite or indexes. These inclusion and exclusion criteria include information that is utilized to identify the collection / cluster of policies under study and also information regarding the variables that have been selected for each. Examples of such criteria consider location perspective (e.g., district, city, region, country), demographics aspects (e.g., age groups), or other dimensions (e.g., gender, education).

UC#1 - Maggioli	UC#2 - Sarga	UC#3 - Sofia	UC#4 - London
Age group	Age group	Location	Age group
Location	Gender	Sub-domain	Gender
Sub-domain	Education	Sector	Education
	Location		Location

The identification of the collection / cluster of policies is performed by means of a list of parameters with their minimum and maximum thresholds that are transformed into specific queries to retrieve the data from the data store. For example, if a dataset from adult population is needed to compute a KPI, a parameter to be included in the population segmentation component (see Section 5.1.1) may include “age” as a variable to be taken into account, along with a “minimum” attribute with a value of “18” and a “maximum” attribute with a value of “60”. Subsequently, this parameter can be transformed into a filter condition of a query that will be applied to retrieve the set of data with the corresponding variables that have to be used for computing such a KPI and thus evaluating the defined policy.

5 Policy Development Toolkit

The present section describes the functionalities of the Policy Development Toolkit (PDT). As a web application, the PDT consists of the front-end that allows policy makers to evaluate Policy Models (PMs), and the backend that hides the complexity of storing the data models into persistent storage and implements the services that the front-end uses to display the content to the user and provide the necessary user experience (UX). The PDT will intentionally hide the complexity of the system data flow to provide the user with a Decision Support System (DSS) towards evidence-based Public Policies (PPs).

5.1 Architecture

The general interconnection of the PDT with the other PolicyCLOUD components is illustrated in Figure 10 below. The PDT enables the processing of data through the exploitation of collective knowledge that emerges from multiple information sources. The platform explores mechanisms that can be clustered across two main areas: analytics on heterogenous data at population and individual level and predefined PMs exploiting community knowledge across different ecosystems. The PDT may be considered as the point of integration and interaction of the platform with the policy makers. Thanks to the PDT, the policy makers are able to query the platform data and exploit the analytics tools through the use of KPIs , in order to create and evaluate PPs.

5.1.1 PDT Design

FIGURE 10: PDT COMMUNICATION COMPONENTS

Figure 10 shows the two components with which the PDT communicates directly: Backend/Datastore and Analytics Tools from the DAA Layer. Both components expose API Interfaces so that the User Interface (UI) receives the data from the Datastore and sends it to the Analytics for processing the parameters that the policy maker has selected through the PME for the respective KPI.

In the proposed architecture each component is decoupled from the others. This modular structure allows versatility and extensibility, by means of analytics tools providers, analytics frameworks, cloud providers and deployment patterns,

while keeping a stable level of trustworthiness. For example, the DAA layer's modularity permits the easy addition of various categories of analytics tools (such as simulation, social network analysis, semantic and linked data etc.), which are earmarked for policy-making purposes. This, in consequence, supports the policy maker in the creation of PMs that are based on the composition of related KPIs. The modular UI intentionally hides the big complexity of the platform's inner processes from users, as each component is decoupled and focused on their own properties and functions (in an object-oriented perspective). So, a PM is composed and supported by related KPIs, which, in turn, are composed of related Analytics Tools that provide their own visualization graphs. A Service Oriented Architecture (SOA) pattern is followed by requiring the components to adhere to a common communication protocol (such as the Analytics Tools registration payload), and by exposing consistent RESTful APIs. This allows different Analytics Tools providers and big data technologies to co-exist and collaborate to create a policy related ecosystem. This modular structure also supports scalability. Each module, depending on the load it receives on a case-by-case basis, can resort to load balancing solutions.

Regarding the modular design of the DAA layer, this allows each Analytics Tool developer to employ different Big Data Analytics (BDAs) frameworks, using various deployment configuration mechanisms. This decoupled and distributed architecture provides fertile ground for the growth of an Analytics Tools Store, where Data Experts may develop specialized Analytics Tools and register them in the PolicyCLOUD platform, via its corresponding DAA layer, which can subsequently be invoked by the PDT using a common data model that the tools must follow (via a common protocol). In consequence, Analytics Tools can operate and provide their services under different financial procedures, including commercialized options. This way, new PMs can be formulated, based on KPIs that utilize Analytics Tools.

In detail, the arrows in Figure 10 show the content of the communication on each side. The policy maker, via the PDT, is able to retrieve a list of existing policies, and view the structure and content of a PM. The display of policies via the PDT is based on the aforementioned PM that is being fed by the data that are stored in the Datastore and are retrieved by the backend services in JSON format.

The User also has access to the registered analytics tools, via the KPIs that are linked with a selected PM. Once an Analytics Tool has been selected for the evaluation of a KPI, the parameter's values are sent to the analytics to start the execution of KPI evaluation. This is being managed by the DAA layer, highlighting our modular approach where each component is only focusing on its own functionality. The PDT provides the user interface that facilitates the policy maker to perform the evaluation, and requests the execution of analytics by communicating with the DAA layer that is responsible for these activities. The user is notified about the submission process, the status of a submitted job, and has the ability to receive and view the results of the Analytics, as the results are communicated to the backend by the DAA layer that monitors the execution of the analysis.

The blue level in Figure 10 represents the process of semantic reasoning and querying. Based on the process set out in Section 3.1, the semantic processing of emerging policies for lifecycle policy modeling intervenes. The metadata provided by this level, together with reasoning, enables the validation of the policy structure in terms of their proper construction. They also help policy makers to choose KPIs, avoid dysfunctional policies, and provide cross-sectional policy optimization information.

The greyed arrows in Figure 10 depict the communication of the DAA layer with the Backend/Datastore which include calls for the invocation of the Analytics Tool, notifications about the status of submitted jobs and their results, as well as queries for data retrieval from the Datastore in order to perform the analytics calculations and produce results. PDT does not access directly the datasets contained in the Datastore but receives the processed / aggregated data produced by the Analytics Tools in the form of a single, properly structured JSON file per each KPI execution. The contents of the JSON file are being forwarded internally to the visualization component for the creation of the proper graph.

FIGURE 11: PME & PDT CONSUMING PDT BACKEND GROUP API FUNCTIONS

Figure 11 shows the detailed graph of interactions of the PDT and PME components with the PDT Backend, depicted at Figure 10. Left is the group of functions exposed with the PDT-Backend RESTful API. PME is consuming functions for the creation/modification of policy models, whereas PDT retrieves policy models in order to run their analytics and get the results back to the policy maker.

The following is a list of basic functions that the PDT provides to the policy makers:

- User Login
- User Profile
- Policy Model Viewer
- Policy Evaluations / Analytics
- Transactions History (This component offers a consistent way of displaying all the Analytics Results that the user has submitted to Analytical Tools along with the selected parameter values)
- Getting Help

A Storyboard suggestion follows:

5.1.1.1 STORYBOARD

INTRODUCTION

After login, the initial page will initiate the PM evaluation process.

We call this component/module ‘policy development toolkit’ by convention, although it helps policy makers to create a real-world policy for example, a political targeting as:

“Do something (like lower the taxes for sugar free products) for population at high risk regarding obesity”.

For our system, a corresponding policy-query (and making/evaluation via controls/menus) could be:

“Identify high risk population regarding obesity” (simplified by what policy maker quantitatively evaluates via wizard)”.

The results may show age group 40-50 male, so the targeting products that are consumed from that group will help the policy maker to create the ‘real world’ policy.

A mockup is shown in Figure 12.

FIGURE 12: MOCKUP: INITIAL PAGE AFTER LOGIN

The policy evaluation steps via the PDT are depicted in the following figure:

FIGURE 13: POLICY EVALUATION STEPS VIA PDT

The PDT guides the user via a step wizard (policy wizard) to follow the hierarchical structure of the policy model. The user submits a job request for the execution of a specific analytics tool for the evaluation of selected KPI. The final step is the retrieval of the Analytics results, which contain the quantitative evaluations and are displayed via the internal visualization component.

POLICY WIZARD

Populate control via PDT backend API

FIGURE 14: POLICY BUILDER WIZARD FOR THE END USERS (MOCKUP)

The user loads a PM from the model’s repository. Each model is associated with some goals/objectives and could include some predefined queries for population segmentation and a list of KPIs.

At page initialization, the KPIs are fetched dynamically from the datastore via the backend exposed API (instead of being hard coded options in the code). This way, KPIs are referring to different entities that can be reused and updated by just adding them in the PDT backend.

Some options can be static; for example, the age, gender, and timeline.

For the rest of controls, appropriate APIs with the available options are offered for policy makers (see below), at the PME design stage.

FIGURE 15: POPULATION SEGMENTATION (IMPLEMENTATION MOCKUP)

FIGURE 16: TIMEFRAME SELECTION OPTION

At initialization of the page, the controls that are dynamically initialized (as mentioned above) are populated with ‘options’ from component/modules such as, e.g., available analytics.

The front-end retrieves the corresponding analytical tools that are related with a specific policy, along with their meta-information, such as the parameters that are expecting, their types, allowed values etc. This information is retrieved by invoking web methods exposed by the backend as REST services. The response of such a request is a JSON object with this information, which allows the front-end accordingly to dynamically draw the content of the page. In order to do so, we have modeled the input parameters that each of the analytical tools will expect. This provides a generic and common way for all tools to describe these parameters so that the front-end of the PDT can invoke all registered tools in a common manner via well-established protocols. This also allows the

frontend of the PDT to become extensible, so as to allow for future tools to be plugged-in and avoid being locked-in to specific implementations. The model definition of the parameters is depicted in Figure 17 below:

FIGURE 17: CLASS DIAGRAM OF THE PARAMETERS

An *AParameter* describes an available parameter required by the analytical tool. It is of a specific type, might contain a list of different constraints, and has a specific evaluation type. When this parameter also has a concrete value, assigned during the runtime, then this value can be of different types, according to the *EvaluationType*.

The *EvaluationType* can be one of the following: EQUAL, LESS, LESS_OR_EQUAL, GREATER, GREATER_OR_EQUAL, IS, NOT, RANGE, IN

The *ValueConstraintType* can be one of the following: DEFAULT, VALUESALLOWED, MIN, MAX, STEP.

The *ParameterValueType* can be one of the following: BOOLEAN, INTEGER, FLOAT, STRING.

For instance, in the aforementioned example, the KPI named *life expectancy* is related to a parameter of type *date*, which accepts a range of values. Therefore, the front-end will retrieve this information via the corresponding REST service to dynamically draw two fields to fill the *from* and *to* values of the *range* and will provide 2 *calendar* objects for the user to insert his/her input during the policy model design (PME). All the selected parameter values are shown in PDT after the user has created the policy model, and the related JSON file has been created into the PDT Backend. To summarize, the backend provides all this information that describes the analytical tools and the front-end provides a wizard to facilitate the start of an analysis. In each of the steps of this wizard, the front-end asks the backend for the corresponding meta-information, and dynamically adjusts to improve the overall UX of the user.

FIGURE 18: INITIALIZATION OF UI CONTROLS FROM THE DATASTORE POLICY MODEL

SUMMARIZE AND SUBMIT

After the initialization of the PDT according to the selected policy and the adjustment of the UI with respect to the meta-information provided by each analytical tool upon its registration, the policy maker is now able to experiment by providing the options to the toolkit and submitting a request for execution of the analytical tool(s).

FIGURE 19: ANALYTICS RESULTS FETCHED FROM THE BACKEND AND VISUALISED IN THE PDT

It should be noted that the PDT does not make policies, but rather assists Policy Makers in policy development, offering a single and integrated entry point (one stop shop approach) to the PolicyCLOUD analytics and Visualization tools.

USER'S HISTORY OF POLICIES

The end user is able to see any of the previously created policy models and their structure (e.g., related KPIs and Analytics Tools).

5.1.2 Data Visualization Framework

The Data Visualization Framework, a sub-component of the PDT, aims to help Policy Makers in the policy creating process, as well as in its subsequent follow-up. This help comes in the form of different charts, graphs, tables, and any other kind of visualization defined, enabling Policy Makers to check in a glance the results of selected data analytics queries outcomes of the previous steps.

FIGURE 20: VISUALIZATION COMMUNICATIONS COMPONENT

The visualization component aims to help Policy Makers on having better insights from their data, previously ingested into the PolicyCloud platform and transformed by the analytical functions. Focusing on this main objective, visualizations charts have been designed with use case owners and stakeholders during meetings and workshops of the project, taking into account their scenarios, their available data and the analytics providers in order to find the more accurate visualization possibilities per each case.

As an initial example we can take the case of Use Case #1 “Participatory policies against radicalization”, Scenario A: Radicalization incidents. The proposed Heat Map turned out to be also feasible, considering the available data. After an initial data review by WP4, it was verified that the available data allows the necessary information to be sent to create the graph. From there, a common format for sending this information was agreed, in order to be received by the Visualization Component and allow it to create the Heat Map. The PDT Backend sends the information in JSON format to the Visualization component, after taking it from the DAA layer. In the figure below we can see one example of the JSON received by the Visualization Component from the PDT Backend, when the chart to create is the Heat Map:

```
{
  "id":2,
  "data": "[{"num_events":4,
    "location":{"type":"Point","coordinates":[-100.5408, 42.642]},
    "location2":{"region":1,"region_txt":"North America"},
    "startDate":341513723145,
    "endDate":972662123145,
    "events":[{"eventId": 201611250026,
      "iyear": "2016",
      "latitude": "47.154901",
      "longitude": "-122.368098",
      "summary": "11/25/2016: Assailants set fire to Our Savior Lutheran Church in Tacoma, Washington, United States. There were no reported casualties in the attack. No group claimed responsibility for the incident."}]}]"
  "typeOfCharts":"HEATMAP_POI"
}
```

FIGURE 21: EXAMPLE OF A JSON FOR A HEAT MAP CHART

Once the Visualization Component receives the json in the agreed format, it can then create the map:

FIGURE 22: EXAMPLE OF A HEAT MAP CHART

Following the same procedure, another scenario that has also been defined was scenario B of the Use Case #2: Intelligent policies for the development of agri-food industry, where the first charts were defined to be a Gauge and a Lineal:

FIGURE 23: EXAMPLE OF A GAUGE CHART

Keywords: vines, vineyard, wine barrel, oenologist

FIGURE 24: EXAMPLE OF A LINEAR CHART

Both charts are very useful in the sentiment analysis process, since they are capable of transmitting a large amount of information quickly and efficiently.

Following the evolution of the project, new visualizations have been added to the component, for example the ones developed for the Use Case #2 scenarios:

- Scenario A1, "Politika price points plus multiple prices": In this scenario, a new type of chart has been developed in order to fulfill the requirements of displaying a 3D data chart in an easy and intuitive way. At this moment this chart is only used by one of the analytical functions used in the project, Politika, but it could be easily reused in case that similar requirements arise.

Name: Multi-factor Pricing Discovery for Aragon vs Competitor Wine in PolicyCLOUD: Ignacio Marin vs Gran Sangre de Toro

Description: Find pricing and ad intensity ratios for an Aragon wine vs a competitor that can provide higher purchase motivation for the Aragon wine than its competitor. Assume that purchase motivation depends on price, quality ad intensity and social influence.

Flip X Y axis Enable color scale Enable border squares Download as image

FIGURE 25: EXAMPLE OF THE CHART USED TO DISPLAY POLITIKA RESULTS

- Scenario A2, “Price evolution”: In this case some improvements to the previous version of the timeline chart have been done in order to show data according to the pilot needs. Basically, the possibility to filter data by specific wine and display their different prices evolutions per vendor has been introduced.

Name: Temporal Evolution of price by winery_name_ontology
Description: temporal evolution of price per name_ontology
Range: 2022-05-07 00:00:00.000 - 2022-06-14 23:59:59.000

FIGURE 26: TIMELINE CHART WITH PRICE EVALUTION DATA

This timeline chart also offers the possibility to compare the data for a specific element in other formats, by clicking over any of the plotted elements.

FIGURE 27: EXAMPLE OF BART CHART

Actually, these types of charts, that have been developed in the frame of the project, can be described as “secondary”, as they are auxiliary charts, used in a primary chart context in order to provide a better understanding of the data received showing them in different formats. They also enable Policy Makers to get more detailed information of the results of the analytical function.

Some of these charts are available in the visualization Heat Map template used in Use Case #1 and #3 scenarios. In this case, the data can be seen in other formats like horizontal bar charts, accumulated bar charts, pie charts. The following figures are examples of this:

FIGURE 28: EXAMPLE OF A HORIZONTAL CHART

FIGURE 29: EXAMPLE OF AN ACCUMULATED BAR CHART

More examples of these secondaries' charts can be found in the primary charts used in the scenarios for Use Case #3, where the bar chart templates enable Policy Makers to view in more detail the information contained in any of the bars:

FIGURE 30: EXAMPLE OF A CLUSTERED COLUMN CHART

Another improvement developed in the component since the last report of the project was the possibility to display the data of some charts in a table format and to export it into 3 different formats: excel, txt and pdf:

FIGURE 31: EXAMPLE OF A CHART WITH ITS RELATED TABLE

Also, the option to display the parameters used to execute the related analytical function has been added and can be displayed by clicking over the button “View parameters”.

FIGURE 32: EXAMPLE OF A CHART WITH THE LIST OF PARAMETERS USED TO LAUNCH THE ANALYTICAL FUNCTION

It is important to highlight that each of these charts will require result data to be provided in a predefined format supported by the chart. Therefore, the analytical tools, after data processing and the generation of the results, need to provide it in the corresponding format in order for the charts to be compatible and in a position to visualize the graph. For that to happen, each tool announces upon registration the type of visualization that its results are compatible with and store the results, respectively. Then, the PDT will be capable to retrieve the results stored in the data repository, check the type of chart that these results are related to, and initialize the graph with the data in the agreed format. At this point of the project, the initial list of charts that need to be supported at this phase, along with the capabilities of each of the available analytical tools, has been identified. This process has not been finished yet, and therefore, the definition of the data format that each chart needs to be compatible with, is still in progress and will be a continuous work until the end of the project.

5.2 Baseline technologies and tools

The PDT is based on a Service Oriented Architecture and consists of the front-end part along with its backend, both aiming to facilitate and ease the interaction of the user with all the analytics components and the Datastore. The front end will be built as a Single Page Application developed using the Angular framework [7]. Angular is “a JavaScript-based open-source front-end web framework mainly maintained by Google and by a community of individuals and corporations to address many of the challenges encountered in developing single-page applications.”¹ The open-sourced full-fledged Angular framework offers multiplatform support without particular hardware or other software requirements. It is based on Typescript programming language and JavaScript (as output) which is compatible with all browsers and mobile devices. For UI components and controls we will use the latest Angular Material library [8].

The Data Visualization Framework has been developed with Angular Framework. Using a framework helps to achieve more functionalities in less time, as it provides reusable components, and makes developers work easier and more efficiently.

¹ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/JavaScript>

With Angular framework, a lot of chart libraries can be used. One of these options could be, for example, amcharts library [9] that provides all possible charts mentioned in 4.1.2, among others. Any other chart library that can be used with Angular can be selected, and the final decision about it will be taken after the final set of charts is selected by end users to better fit their use cases.

Finally, the backend implementation of the PDT will be based on the Java release 8 [10], which can be easily installed and run in different environments. Additionally, according to the Service Oriented Architecture paradigm, it will implement and expose various REST APIs that will be used by the other components of the PDT. The REST web services will follow the JAX-RS specification, as described in the corresponding JSR-331 [11], JSR-339 [12] and JSR-370 [13] Java specification requests. The library that the backend will rely on for the implementation of these specifications will be Jersey [14]. The deployment of the backend will be using an embedded Java servlet container, to avoid the need to maintain an entire application server. The whole backend will be packaged in a single Java Archive (Jar) to ease the overall deployment. For the data repository of the PDT, we will rely on the LXS relational datastore that is the main pillar of the data management component of PolicyCLOUD.

6 Legal and Ethical Constraints

6.1 Constraints related to User Data

The information collected and stored in the PDT backend can essentially be divided into two categories:

- **Policy Data**, meaning the data which is collected from identified data sources and further processed by the Analytics Tools in the PDT backend, to generate relevant outputs for the PolicyCLOUD users (in the form of selected data visualizations);
- **User Data**, meaning the data which is collected from the actual individual users of the PDT, to allow the creation of user accounts and the general functioning of the PDT.

This information may be classifiable as “personal data”, to the extent that it can be traced back to natural person. Concerns which arise as a result of Policy Data are described in D3.3 [15] and D3.6 [16], and should specifically be addressed by the different partners in charge of use cases, considering: (1) the data sources which the policy maker indicates as relevant for each use case scenario, including any legal/contractual constraints specific to their use, (2) the specific types of data to be collected from those data sources, and (3) the purposes for which the use case partners wish to have those data processed.

Where the PolicyCLOUD system is concerned, the main focus is on user Data, as the PME/PDT will serve as the entry point for such data and requires such data in order to function. Therefore, as outlined in D3.3 [15] and D3.6 [16], the following concerns have been or are being addressed:

1. **Lawfulness.** An appropriate legal basis for each purpose for which personal data on users may be collected has been identified, under Art. 6 GDPR. All steps needed to properly implement the identified legal bases have been taken, depending on the legal bases selected, which in turn depends on the way user personal data are processed via the PDT. The legal bases are:
 - Compliance with legal requirements, under Art. 6(1)(c) GDPR;
 - The legitimate interests of the PolicyCLOUD Manager(s) and users (or the organisations to which users belong) to ensure the proper operation of the PDT/PME and overall PolicyCLOUD platform, under Art. 6(1)(f) GDPR;
 - The legitimate interests of the PolicyCLOUD Manager(s) and users (or the organisations to which users belong) to ensure the security of the PDT/PME and overall PolicyCLOUD platform, as well as of data stored on the platform, under Art. 6(1)(f) GDPR;
 - The legitimate interests of the PolicyCLOUD Manager(s) in leveraging personal data as needed for the establishment, exercise, or defence of legal claims (e.g., brought against the PolicyCLOUD Manager(s) for damages resulting from use of the PDT/PME), under Art. 6(1)(f) GDPR.
2. **Fairness.** Personal data on users is not used in a manner which may violate their reasonable expectations. Users are not profiled, and their data is not covertly shared with third parties for marketing purposes. Also, mechanisms are in place to ensure that users can exercise their rights in relation to any personal data of theirs which may be collected during the use of the PDT/PME. More specifically, each data subject will be able to exercise the following rights by sending a request in writing to the PolicyCLOUD Manager(s), to the extent permitted by applicable law:
 - To access. Data subjects can obtain information relating to the processing of their personal data and a copy of such personal data;

- To erase. Data subjects can require the deletion of their personal data, to the extent permitted by law;
 - To object. Data subjects can object to the processing of their personal data, on grounds relating to their situation. Where an objection is presented, the PolicyCLOUD Manager(s) will be entitled to assess the request, and refuse the request if there are legitimate reasons to proceed with the processing that prevail over the freedoms, interests, and rights of the requesting data subject;
 - To rectify. Where data subjects consider that their personal data is inaccurate or incomplete, they can require that such personal data be modified accordingly;
 - To restrict. Data subjects can request the restriction of the processing of their personal data. Furthermore, should data subjects believe that the processing of their personal data is contrary to the legislation in force, they have the right to lodge a complaint to the competent data protection supervisory authority.
3. **Transparency.** A specific privacy policy has been developed for the PDT, to provide written information to users as to how their personal data may be handled when using the PDT in a concise, transparent, intelligible, and easily accessible form, using clear and plain language, meeting all the requirements of Arts. 13 and 14 GDPR. An initial version of this privacy policy for the PDT – which is arguably extensible, with minor adaptations, to other platforms relevant to the Project, such as the PME or the Incentives Management tool – is attached to D8.1 [17]. This document will be further revised with the Consortium and adapted over time, as part of the ongoing implementation of the legal/regulatory and ethical/societal requirements identified in D3.3 [15] and D3.6 [16] - progress on this will be reported in the upcoming D3.9 Deliverable. More specifically, the data protection information notice is provided to PDT users using a two-layer approach:
- The first layer is represented by a pop-up banner which is shown to users when accessing the PDT. This pop-up banner includes a link to the second layer data protection information notice (i.e., the extended version of the data protection information notice). The text of the pop-up banner is provided in D8.1 [17].
 - The second layer is represented by the extended version of the data protection information notice, including all elements required by Arts 13 and 14 GDPR. This extended version of the data protection information notice, the text of which is provided under D8.1 [17], is accessible to PDT users by clicking on a footer named “End Users Data Protection Information Notice” published on all the pages of the PDT’s web environment.

Additionally, it is important to note that the PDT and PME do not use cookies or similar tracking technologies, so no specific compliance requirements are needed to this regard.

4. **Purpose limitation.**

Personal data collected on PDT/PME users is not used for purposes which are incompatible with those declared in the privacy policy, which are:

- Creation and management of the end user account and operation of the platform.
 - Ensuring the security and the proper use of the platform.
 - To defend PolicyCLOUD from legal and/or regulatory risks.
5. **Data minimization.** Only the strict minimum amount of personal data needed for the above listed purposes are collected. More specifically, the personal data of PDT/PME users processed are the following:
- Name;
 - E-mail address;
 - Organisation and role;
 - Username and password;
 - IP address;

- Event logs related to the use of the platform
6. **Accuracy.** Users are given the possibility to rectify any personal data they submit, or which is collected on them, in connection with use of the PDT/PME, by sending a request in writing to PolicyCLOUD;
 7. **Storage limitation.** Personal data on PDT/PME users may only be stored for the strict minimum amount of time needed to meet any of the purposes for which they were lawfully collected, after which the personal data should be irreversibly anonymized or deleted. This requires the identification of appropriate retention periods for any such personal data collected.
 8. **Security.** Appropriate security measures to ensure the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of any collected and further stored personal data, as well as the resilience of systems used to collect and further store those data, must be implemented.
 9. **Accountability.** Records of evidence showing compliance with these requirements must be kept.

6.2 Constraints related to PolicyCLOUD Use

From the contractual perspective, terms and conditions have been defined for the acceptable use of the PolicyCLOUD, to properly regulate the service relationship established between PolicyCLOUD users, or the organization to which PolicyCLOUD users belong. These terms and conditions need to be accepted for use of the PolicyCLOUD to be allowed and form a binding contract upon PolicyCLOUD users / their organizations.

Matters regulated within these terms and conditions include:

1. Description of the services offered through the PolicyCLOUD system;
2. Payment terms (if applicable);
3. Rules on acceptable use of the PolicyCLOUD;
4. Intellectual property (in particular, ownership of the PolicyCLOUD assets, the Policy Data and the PolicyCLOUD output);
5. Data protection (with reference to the privacy policy, as well as to a data management agreement or similar arrangement which may be put in place between the end-user and PolicyCLOUD);²
6. Warranties and liability related to provision of the PolicyCLOUD system, in particular, considering the likelihood of statistical inaccuracies in output presented by the PolicyCLOUD and the use of such output to create public policies;
7. Warranties provided by the PolicyCLOUD user/their organization, and, in particular, compliance with legal and ethical requirements around selection of data sources and use of the PolicyCLOUD for policy making purposes;
8. Applicable law;
9. Modification of the terms and conditions;
10. Termination and effects of termination;

² When offering the PDT and/or PME as a service, the PolicyCLOUD Manager(s) may be acting, simultaneously, as a controller for some activities involving personal data and as a processor on behalf of the end-users. As such, entering a standard DPA under Art. 28 GDPR may not suffice to fully regulate the data processing relationship between the PolicyCLOUD Manager(s) and PDT users, as this would only cover the processor activities of the PolicyCLOUD Manager(s). To comprehensively regulate this relationship, the arrangement will need to include obligations to govern the PolicyCLOUD Manager(s) personal data processing activities as a controller. This can be done through a Data Management Agreement (DMA, which distinguishes between the different sets of processing activities performed and allocates different corresponding sets of obligations to each party, to ensure that it is clear to what extent each party will be responsible for complying with the different controller obligations laid out in the GDPR.

11. Other matters which may require contractual regulation, depending on the specific services to be provided.

6.3 Constraints related to Data Visualization

The data visualization component should ideally not actually rely on or disclose information about identifiable individuals, but instead rely on appropriately aggregated data, which cannot be traced back to any given specific and identified individual, to avoid raising personal data protection concerns regarding data manipulated by PDT users. Where it is feasible, the core concerns around data visualization will focus on:

1. **Statistical accuracy.** Indeed, a failure to provide appropriate visualization results may ultimately lead to misleading or erroneous conclusions drawn by policymakers, culminating in misguided policy-making activities. As such, the Consortium should ensure that enough testing is performed to ensure a reasonable degree of statistical accuracy for these activities. Any operations performed on data should be methodically logged to ensure traceability, and the general rationale and logic behind the data visualization should be explained to PDT users, so this can be considered during their decision-making process. Users should be advised of the possibility of false positives or false negatives and errors in result presentation, so that they are incentivised to critically examine results produced by the visualization functions in their decision-making process.
2. **Explainability of results.** For a PDT user to make use of the PDT in a meaningful way, as a tool to support policymaking while preserving their own accountability for the decisions taken regarding any specific policy, it is important that they can understand the output presented to them by the PDT. Several different means can be conceived of to provide this information to users. The most appropriate form of delivery, considering the UX and context when operating the PDT, should be further assessed. Clear explanations should be given to users on:
 3. Steps taken across the design and implementation of the PDT and overall PolicyCLOUD platform to ensure compliance with applicable legal and ethical requirements, in particular those implemented to maximise the security and robustness of the platform, as well as the accuracy and reliability of output;
 4. The types of data sources and data used to produce outputs;
 5. The rationale behind outputs, in terms of explaining generically how the data sources and data were processed to generate the outputs in question;

The likelihood of statistical inaccuracies in the outputs and the importance of critical examination and validation of output implications for policymaking by the user. The above requirements have been condensed (among other requirements applicable to components developed under WP5) into the **WP5 Legal/Ethical Checklist**, which serves to keep track of each requirement and progress made on its implementation, as the project develops.

7 Conclusion

This document is the third and final release of deliverable D5.2 [1] submitted in September 2020 and deliverable D5.4 [2] submitted in August 2021. It establishes the definition of the Public Policies (PPs) in the context of the PolicyCLOUD project and presents the methodologies based on ontologies and semantic reasoning that are being used for modelling of PPs. Moreover, it describes the specifications of the tools and technologies used in the Policy Model Editor, as well as the design of the Policy Development Toolkit (including the visualization framework), and the mechanisms required for the compilation of policy collections to perform cross-sector analysis. Finally, it details the legal, ethical and privacy constraints and requirements related to WP5 activities.

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